

Spectrophotometric Estimation of Vanadium (V) with 2-2'- Diamino-Diphenyl-Disulphide

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Manuscript received 11 March 1976, revised 5 November 1976, accepted 10 November 1976

Vanadium forms a reddish violet complex with 2-2'-diamino-diphenyl-disulphide in the presence of H_2SO_4 or HCl. The complex has an extinction co-efficient of 1.9×10^3 and obeys Beer's law between 15-50 ppm. The molar composition of the complex is found to be 1:2. Interference of various cations and anions have been reported.

N-(1-MERCAPTOPHENYL)-N'-phenyl-thio-urea; a derivative of ortho amino-benzene thiol has been used by us¹ as a chelating agent for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} . Our present investigation relates to the use of the dimer of ortho-amino-benzene-thiol namely 2,2'-diamino-diphenyl-disulphide as a reagent for the spectrophotometric estimation of Vanadium (V).

Experimental

2,2'-diamino-diphenyl-disulphide (DADPDS) was prepared by the method given in the literature². Its 1 per cent solution in alcohol was used as a reagent.

Standard solution of Vanadium(V) (500 ppm) was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of ammonium-meta-vanadate in distilled water and was standardised by the method given in the literature³.

Procedure: To a solution containing upto 50 μg . of Vanadium(V) is added 3 ml. of 1 per cent ligand solution. The acidity of the solution is adjusted between 1 and 2 molar with H_2SO_4 in a total volume of 25 ml. The solution is diluted to 25 ml. with alcohol and absorbance of the solution is recorded after 20 mins at 520 nm. The amount of metal present in the solution is then determined from the calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Spectral studies and effect of acidity: In order to study the effect of acidity on the absorbance of the complex a series of solutions containing a fixed amount of metal (1 ml. of 500 ppm) and excess of ligand (3 ml of 1 per cent solution) were prepared. The acidities of the solutions were adjusted between 0.5 to 5 molar with H_2SO_4 in a total volume of 25 ml and the absorption spectra were recorded against the corresponding reagent blank. It was found that the complex shows maximum absorption at 520 nm when the molar concentration of the acid is between 1 and 2.

For full colour development 3 ml of 1 per cent ligand is required. The colour of the complex attains stability 20 mins after the addition of reagent and remains so for more than an hour and a half.

Physico-chemical constants of the complex: Linearity between absorbance and metal ion has been observed in the concentration range of 15-50 ppm of Vanadium.

The sensitivity of the colour reaction in terms of Sandell's definition is 0.027 $\mu g/cm^2$ for $\log I_0/I = 0.001$ at 520 nm. The molar absorptivity calculated from a plot of Beer's law is 1.9×10^3 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

The average of the three determinations with 0.045 mg of Vanadium(V) is 0.04466 mg which varies between 0.045 mg and 0.044 mg with 99.24 per cent confidence limit. Molar composition of the complex was determined by Job's method of continuous variation⁴. In Job's method the maximum in the curve is obtained when the ratio of metal to ligand is 1:2.

Effect of diverse ions: The tolerance limits of various cations and anions are: Bi^{3+} (1:75); Cd^{2+} (1:10); Cr^{3+} (1:1); Be^{2+} (1:75); Zr^{4+} (1:7.5); Th^{4+} (1:3); U^{6+} (1:7.5); Zn^{2+} (1:10); Ni^{2+} (1:2.5); Mn^{2+} (1:5); Cl^- (1:10); ClO_4^- (1:10); Br^- (1:7.5); $B_4O_7^{2-}$ (1:7.5); MeO_4^- (1:5); NO_3^- (1:5); WO_4^{2-} (1:1). Interference caused by ions like Pb^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} which are generally present in the Vanadate ores is eliminated by using HCl to adjust the acidity instead of H_2SO_4 .

References

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